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Oportunidades para la adaptación social de la primera infancia en el seno familiar

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Resumen. El estudio del comportamiento social ha generado un enfoque interdisciplinario entre psicología, psicología social y sociología. Esta convergencia teórica permite abordar la adaptación social como expresión clave de la autoidentificación individual y su evolución, destacando su relevancia en el análisis contemporáneo de las dinámicas sociales y personales. Se exponen los resultados de un estudio realizado en 2023 con 17 familias con niños pequeños, caracterizadas por condiciones adversas (en términos de relaciones conyugales, condiciones de vida y niveles de ingresos), los hallazgos revelaron indicios de hipersocialización autoritaria, en la que el énfasis en un modelo de comportamiento deseado no siempre se alinea con las normas sociales que rigen la crianza de las generaciones más jóvenes. En cambio, en familias con condiciones más favorables, los desafíos de la crianza tienden a centrarse en el bienestar material, la salud de los hijos y los padres, y los desacuerdos sobre los métodos de crianza adecuados. La influencia de la generación anterior (abuelos) desempeña un papel significativo en la configuración de la dinámica familiar. Los niños criados en hogares disfuncionales o monoparentales presentan diferencias marcadas en comparación con sus compañeros. Tienden a tener baja autoestima, lo que a menudo se vincula a conflictos familiares que afectan negativamente a su bienestar moral y emocional. Por el contrario, en familias donde ambos cónyuges contribuyen por igual al presupuesto familiar, organizan actividades de ocio y comparten la responsabilidad de la crianza, el proceso de socialización de los niños tiende a ser más exitoso.

Palabras clave: familia, mentalidad azerbaiyana, relaciones madre-hijo, primera infancia, análisis sociológico.

Opportunities for the social adaptation of early childhood within the family

Abstract. The study of social behavior has generated an interdisciplinary approach between psychology, social psychology and sociology. This theoretical convergence allows us to address social adaptation as a key expression of individual self-identification and its evolution, highlighting its relevance in the contemporary analysis of social and personal dynamics. The results of a study conducted in 2023 with 17 families with young children, characterized by adverse conditions (in terms of marital relationships, living conditions, and income levels), are presented, the findings revealed indications of authoritarian hypersocialization, in which the emphasis on a desired behavior model does not always align with the social norms that govern the upbringing of younger generations. Instead, in families with more favorable conditions, parenting challenges tend to focus on material well-being, the health of children and parents, and disagreements about appropriate parenting methods. The influence of the previous generation (grandparents) plays a significant role in shaping family dynamics. Children raised in dysfunctional or single-parent homes have marked differences compared to their peers. They tend to have low self-esteem, which is often linked to family conflicts that negatively affect their moral and emotional well-being. Conversely, in families where both spouses contribute equally to the family budget, organize leisure activities, and share responsibility for parenting, the process of socializing children tends to be more successful.

Key words: family, Azerbaijani mentality, mother-child relationships, early childhood, sociological analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The study of the family represents one of the critical areas of research in social pedagogy. In this context, all significant issues should be examined from a socio-practical perspective. The processes occurring within the family, particularly conflicts between spouses, among other factors, have become subjects of study across multiple branches of psychology and pedagogy. The information obtained plays a vital role in understanding the mechanisms of intra-family communication. The family is a small group with unique developmental characteristics. Tradition plays a crucial role within the family, which functions as a closed system with members of different ages, and the relationships among them are long-term; individuals assume various roles and functions within the family. The role of communication within the family is considerable (Smelser, 1994; Chen et al., 2013; Hamidova, 2020), and close interaction, attachment, and the emotional tone of the relationships are notably high (Reid et al., 2007; Theiss, 2018).

In the study of the process of child socialization within the family, it is essential to account for the distinctive features of the particular family in question. Clearly, this refers to a young family. Indeed, young families are where small children are born. From this arises the structure, role distribution, and the status of the husband and wife, as well as their interactions within the family, which depend primarily on the age of the newlyweds and the stage of their family life. When considering the Azerbaijani family, it is noteworthy that, as in other parts of the world, there is a trend toward

an increasing age of marriage. In other words, marriage typically occurs around the ages of 27 to 30 years. Over the past decade, the average age of marriage for men has increased by two years, reaching 30.2 years in 2023, while for women; it has risen by one and a half years to 25.2 years (AZERTAC, 2024). If young individuals marry within traditional frameworks, their relationships within the family are also likely to be based on traditions that emphasize the husband's high status within the family. Consequently, the woman is often assigned the roles of mother and homemaker. These dynamics influence the nature of child-rearing, the education of the child, and the child's adaptation to both the family and social environment.

In recent years, the number of divorces has increased, even within the first five years of marriage. (Compared to 2022, the number of marriages per 1,000 people has decreased from 6.1 to 5.3, while the number of divorces has increased from 1.6 to 2.) This shift undoubtedly impacts the upbringing and socialization of the younger generation (The State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2024).

Moreover, egalitarian trends have been strengthening within modern Azerbaijani families, where family roles are distributed more equally. However, this does not always result in the normalization of family relations. The number of civil marriages is steadily rising, as well as the number of children born outside of marriage. Therefore, in the study of early childhood social adaptation in contemporary young Azerbaijani families, it is essential to consider these developmental characteristics at each stage of the family's evolution. Over the past few decades, the number of children in families has been declining, whether in urban or rural settings. Consequently, children are often raised as only children, with two children in a family being rare. This trend undoubtedly affects the process of adaptation to the social environment. Contemporary social conditions also influence the development of family relations, particularly in households where young children are being raised (Kazimli, 2020). The digitalization of society, globalization, environmental degradation, and regional and international political processes often lead to international conflicts, which in turn affect the development of the younger generation, its upbringing, and the formation of individual identities. These observations provide the foundation for addressing the issue of socialization and adaptation of young children in modern Azerbaijani families.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The primary focus in examining parent-child relationships during early childhood lies in the analysis of their socio-psychological characteristics. At the core of this examination is the parents' evaluation of the child's personality, innate qualities, emotional world, and volitional manifestations. Psychologists have made significant contributions to the study of parent-child interactions on a personal level. The pioneers of psychological thought have thoroughly explored human development across different age stages, identifying distinctive characteristics, levels of personal maturity, and the potential for socialization in diverse social contexts (Kon, 1989; Lerner, 2002; Belinskaya & Tikhomandritskaya, 2003; Obukhova, 2006; Belasheva & Makadey, 2016). Additionally, numerous scholars in the field of pedagogy have contributed to this discourse (Rabbi Yisroel Roll, 2016).

This article aims to analyze social adaptation within the framework of the socialization of young children in both stable and dysfunctional family environments.

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology consists of a systematic analysis and interpretation of data derived from approaches presented in the academic literature, as well as validated survey questionnaires. Was used the questionnaire of parental attitudes (Varg & Stolin, 2014). This is a psychodiagnostic tool aimed at identifying parental attitudes on issues of raising children and communicating with them.

The study was also conducted on the basis of a specially designed questionnaire:

1. Does the child tell his parents what is in his heart? Is he sincere?
2. What is the sense of security known from?
 - In the emotional-volitional spheres: memory, attention, perception, etc.
 - In the physical sphere: physical health, agility, overcoming fear in games, etc.
 - How is it ensured from a technical point of view?
 - How is it ensured from a psychological point of view (motivation, etc.).
3. What is the stability or instability in the family known from (if any, identify and describe the cases):
 - Habits, actions that can lead to asocial behavior (drunkenness, marital infidelity, rudeness, cruelty)
 - Child crimes, alcoholism, drug addiction and other pathological phenomena
4. What social assistance is provided to this family by society? How is social and pedagogical support provided for the social adaptation (adaptation) of children?
5. The inner movement of a person towards perfection is to ensure his freedom; is his upbringing carried out as a need for freedom, independent, free activity, initiative and desire for responsibility?
6. How is the complementarity of individual and social interests realized here?
7. How is interaction with the child carried out?
 - Playing joint games (how much, i.e. how many times a day or a week, for what period, where, in what form)
 - Are feelings of care, collectivism instilled? How?
8. Pedagogical culture of parents:
 - Acquaintance with pedagogical literature
 - receiving pedagogical advice
 - are they able to solve the pedagogical problem that has arisen, for example, children are fighting over a toy, or do not want to go home, other life examples

9. Are parents hypocritical and indifferent to their children? How to determine this:
 - The child does not share his problems
 - The parents are closed, insincere, and cold
10. If only one parent is raising a child in a family, is alimony paid here? Does the other parent participate in the upbringing? How?
11. If there are fights at home, indicate the reason.
12. If violence is used against children, indicate.
13. Has the assistance of educational and social institutions been used? (Social assistance, children's room, boarding school, etc.). How is assistance provided to problem families and children here (child protection centers, social services, shelters) (it is necessary to include information related to the area of the study). In what form do rehabilitation and adaptation centers operate?
14. Is work carried out with problem families by relevant institutions? Health workers, school teachers, social workers, police, etc.
15. Is the assistance of institutions engaged in the implementation of adaptation and rehabilitation of the child's development, behavior sought?
 - Are social-psychological and pedagogical counseling services and centers, speech therapy rooms in children's clinics, special groups for children with mental retardation, chronic diseases, etc. created, and are appeals made to them?
16. How is children's leisure activities organized?

That is, what kind of entertainment, games, and sports are they engaged in, and what organizations are they addressed to?
17. How are children prepared for the educational process?
18. Are there any violations of the structure and functions of the family? In what?
19. What is the standard of living: per capita incomes in the family (calculates and write down), what are the conditions for keeping children (give a brief description)
20. Is there an increase in psycho-emotional overload in parents?
21. Education of parents (show)
22. Have they applied to social shelters, do parents have any idea about this in general?
23. Are there differences in the training and upbringing of girls and boys? What is known?
24. Have there been cases of removing a child from an asocial family in order to change the conditions that threaten their life, health and full development?
25. Indicate and comment on cases of providing primary medical and psychological-pedagogical assistance to eliminate the immediate consequences of psycho-traumatic factors, determine the individual and behavioral characteristics, the degree of deprivation of the child, and determine the ways of primary socio-pedagogical rehabilitation.

26. characterize the family's housing and living conditions: per capita housing area, what is the house (apartment) they live in, positive and negative aspects, in what area (i.e. where in the city)
27. Family composition, how many people are there, who they are
28. Child's health indicators: how many times a year (month) is doctors consulted, for what reasons, what is the result, etc. How many points can parents assess the child's quality of life out of 10?
29. What forms and opportunities of state assistance are valued by parents, why, what are their recommendations?
30. In what psychological-pedagogical issues is the help of a psychologist needed?
31. How is family policy assessed by parents?

RESULTS

An examination of sociological and psychological literature reveals several distinctive features of the socialization process from the perspective of the internal dynamics of social groups. Western scholars emphasize that

“an effective leader will never exercise power in a directive or predictable manner. On the contrary, a positive or socialized leader focuses more on realizing group objectives by assisting in their identification, providing the necessary resources for their attainment, supporting group members, and affirming the competencies of each individual” (Meskon et al., 1992: 225).

The principal forms of power include coercion, reward, expertise, example, and tradition. A leader may also exert influence through rational belief, participatory decision-making, and persuasion. As a micro-social group, the family constructs its internal relationships and communication based on these principles, playing an active role in shaping and socializing the younger generation. It is essential to recognize the role of both participants in the adaptation process—parents and the child.

Erik H. Erikson (1996: 15) conceptualized personality as a process of “organizing life experience into an individual self,” which inherently implies its dynamic nature throughout a person's lifetime. The fundamental function of this personality structure is adaptation in the broadest sense. According to Erikson (1996: 8-9), the process of personality formation and development “preserves the integrity and individuality of human experience... enables individuals to anticipate both internal and external events, mitigate threats, and balance their capabilities with the social opportunities provided by society”.

Erikson (1996: 13) defines personality as a complex individual construct with a multi-layered structure, linked to three primary levels of human nature analysis: individual, personal, and social. Accordingly, adaptation can be understood primarily as a set of personality traits formed on the basis of identity. A shift in identity also serves as an indicator of successful adaptation within the socialization process. Consequently, a distinct style of social behavior emerges, wherein one aspect is shaped by intra-group relations, while the other reflects the individual's unique personal characteristics.

In a broader sense, social identity—an outcome of social adaptation—stems from an individual's self-identification with various social categories (i.e., group affiliations) and, alongside personal identity, constitutes a crucial regulator of social behavior.

A study was conducted to investigate the role of parent-child relationships in the social adaptation of children within Azerbaijani families. The survey involved 17 families (eight stable and nine dysfunctional), utilizing the "Parental Attitude Diagnostic Method" developed by Stolín (Rogov, 1996).

As is well known, the process of forming social identity and social adaptation reaches completion when an individual internalizes the norms and stereotypes of their social groups, integrating them as intrinsic regulators of social behavior. This phenomenon is particularly evident in young children. In this context, value orientations and social orientations play a crucial role. Given the intricate structure of human behavior, an individual act can be seen as the fundamental social unit of behavior, its primary function being to establish alignment between a basic social situation and the subject's social need(s). The primary responsibility of a parent is to regulate these behaviors in a manner that fosters the child's development as an individual while ensuring conformity to essential social requirements.

However, families differ significantly, and as a result, the initial conditions for children's socialization vary widely. Numerous socio-psychological factors contribute to the contradictions in role distribution within the family. Among the key objective factors underlying these contradictions are the following:

- 1) Improvements in the material well-being of family members, leading to heightened material and spiritual needs;
- 2) The increasing inability of men to fully meet these evolving needs;
- 3) The growing prominence of women's social roles and the radical transformation of their societal status;
- 4) A shift in women's value systems, prioritizing public engagement and professional activity over traditional domestic roles;
- 5) The weakening of adaptive mechanisms that historically structured role distribution within the family;
- 6) A decline in maternal instincts and traditional maternal responsibilities;
- 7) A widening gap between women's roles in domestic life and their engagement in public and professional spheres;
- 8) The erosion of traditional gender roles within urban lifestyles;
- 9) The emergence of significant gaps in conventional domains of familial and social upbringing.

These factors collectively undermine the structure of role distribution, leading to the gradual disintegration of family traditions, stability, and the centuries-old order that once defined familial cohesion.

The erosion of mutual understanding within the family plays a significant role in the development of conflicts. As comprehension between family members deteriorates, cognitive distortions emerge, leading to shifts in patterns of thinking. Misleading self-narratives and distorted perceptions of others take root, impairing the ability to objectively assess reality. In such cases, self-regulation weakens, making it increasingly difficult to exercise control over interpersonal dynamics.

Consequently, family interactions become reactive in nature, heavily influenced by external factors such as peer relationships, parental expectations, and culturally ingrained customs. This reactivity diminishes the individual's ability to engage in independent decision-making and adaptive problem-solving, further complicating the dynamics of familial and social relationships.

If these false "myths" dominate the process of family formation, the family will be governed by a "double" morality and mutual disillusionment in the perception of each other's personalities. To prevent this, every couple should seek guidance from a psychologist. The psychologist's role is to dispel these myths and help each individual accept the personality of the other in its entirety, as it truly is, thereby ensuring the longevity and success of the family unit.

It has been observed that individuals, through their formal psychological traits, attempt to distance themselves from an unfamiliar environment while simultaneously striving to alter it. Conflicts between cohabiting spouses arise when their respective "zones" of interaction do not sufficiently overlap. For instance, a rigid individual may struggle to coexist with a more adaptable partner. The former exhibits heightened attentional control and demands a high degree of organization and order from their surroundings. Meanwhile, the adaptable individual structures their environment according to their own preferences, leading to antagonistic external conditions. This discord results in decreased work efficiency, weakened cognitive functions, increased emotional tension, psychological discomfort, and ultimately, conflict between spouses. In such a scenario, one partner is inevitably compelled to compromise their own needs for the sake of the other.

In the contemporary world, parents possess greater means to shield their children from psychological distress. They seek to monitor the books their children read, the music they listen to, and the television programs they watch, fearing the potentially detrimental influence of mass media. However, paradoxically, many parents fail to recognize their own relationships as an external influence on their children. Indeed, children who are exposed to familial conflict are at a significantly higher risk of developing psychological and behavioral issues.

This issue is particularly pronounced in families where parenting disagreements arise. Studies conducted by South Korean scholars indicate that children exposed to divergent parenting styles exhibit a higher prevalence of behavioral problems. For example, if one parent enforces strict disciplinary measures, while the other adopts a more permissive approach, the child may experience confusion and internal conflict. Parenting challenges extend beyond mere disagreements; they can have a lasting psychological impact on children, often necessitating psychological intervention.

Moreover, in the context of social adaptation, particular attention must be paid to the development of a child's self-perception. The structure of a single-parent household, particularly when led by a mother, presents significant economic hardships compared to those faced by single fathers. Research has identified divorce as the primary cause of single-parent families. Several key factors contribute to divorce, including premature marriage before psychological readiness for family life, an inability to adapt to socio-economic demands, substance abuse, and excessive familial interference in marital affairs.

According to child psychotherapist Rabbi Israel Roll, children exhibit three primary negative reactions to parental conflict. First, their capacity for accurate emotional assessment declines sharply, underscoring the need for educational and emotional security. As Roll asserts, "Children require a sense of protection within their educational and emotional environments."

When parental discord disrupts this security, the child's world is fundamentally shaken." Second, children often internalize guilt for parental conflicts. Given their egocentric perception of the world, they may believe that their actions are the cause of familial discord, even in cases where they bear no responsibility. Finally, children may attempt to disengage entirely from the conflict. Roll emphasizes that when parents enter therapy exhibiting resistance or a lack of enthusiasm, it is imperative that they undergo therapy together with their children. As he states, "A child's behavioral responses often serve as an attempt to comprehend the dynamics between their parents" (Rabbi Yisroel Roll, 2016).

The most prevalent issue in such single-parent families is one related to the economic, or material, standard of living. It is evident that the state should take into account the number of single-parent families, classify them into specific categories, and provide a certain level of social assistance based on these classifications. In the majority of single-parent households, the head of the family is a woman. In certain situations, no matter how much effort a woman puts into fulfilling the role of the head of the household alone, she may eventually become exhausted, which can contribute to the deterioration of the family structure. The root cause of this issue should be examined through the lens of social problems. It is noteworthy that the number of children born outside of marriage has increased in Azerbaijan. In 2022, the mother of every seventh child born in the country was not legally married (BAKUPLUS, 2024).

A single parent must take responsibility for the education and upbringing of their children, ensuring that they attain a socially beneficial position in society so that negative perceptions of the family can be altered. These families should receive moral support from friends, relatives, and, in certain cases, social workers. Only under such circumstances can both individual and systemic challenges be addressed, allowing these families to be regarded as integral units of society.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

When categorizing families into two groups, various indicators influencing family lifestyle, role distribution, and child-rearing approaches were considered. As an example, the study presents data comparing a stable (healthy) family and a problematic family.

Stable Family: This family consists of both a mother and a father, with two daughters. The per capita income is 300 manats (approximately 177 USD). The father is employed, while the mother is engaged in raising the children at home. They reside in a five-room house and have been married for approximately seven years. Their elder daughter is five years old, and the younger one is two. Over the course of their marriage, they have encountered only one major problem, which was eventually resolved. The child is respected as an individual, and their opinion is sought and considered. The father's salary varies annually.

Problematic Family: This is a single-parent household. The mother has passed away. One child is five years old, while the other is eighteen. Although the older child has adapted to the loss of the mother, the younger child has struggled to do so. The family resides in a four-room house, with a per capita income of 325 manats (approximately 190 USD). The father is employed, and the grandmother takes care of the children.

Upon analyzing the two families previously described, it can be concluded that, in a healthy family dynamic, the mutual influence and shared interests between family members serve to strengthen the family unit. Furthermore, the equal attention given to the child by both the father and the mother fosters a nurturing environment. In such families, children exhibit increased initiative and a growing sense of independence.

In the case of the dysfunctional family, the primary issue is the death of the mother. However, aside from this tragedy, the family demonstrates a positive attitude toward the child and endeavors to mitigate the negative consequences of this traumatic event. It is highly likely that the children would benefit from consulting a psychologist.

The research was also conducted at the A.S. Pushkin Secondary School in the Tovuz district. The results revealed that a significant number of students live in dysfunctional family environments. Naturally, it is evident that all children experience challenges. Nevertheless, when we specified that the research should focus solely on children from incomplete and other problematic family structures, the psychologist responded that they could not provide an exact figure for such children, though they acknowledged their existence. When asked about the methods employed in working with children from dysfunctional families, the psychologist stated that they utilized a counseling approach but were unfamiliar with corrective or psychotherapeutic techniques. When I inquired whether the psychologist considered the individual differences between children during their work, I was surprised by their response. The psychologist mentioned that they treated all children equally and noted that many children were apprehensive about engaging in conversation with them.

However, it seemed that the psychologist was not particularly concerned about this situation. It is important to clarify that when we speak of differences among children, we refer to variations in age, family circumstances, financial status, and the quality of intra-family relationships. After concluding our discussion with the psychologist, we approached the 8-B grade, which consists of the most challenging students. In a conversation with the class teacher, it was revealed that the teacher had repeatedly warned parents about their children's behavior. As a result of these warnings, some children exhibited positive improvements, while others showed the opposite trend. It is known that the parents of the children who demonstrated progress took the matter seriously, though it would be inappropriate to make the same claim about the others. The class teacher mentioned that they had spoken with the children and advised the parents to seek psychological counseling for their children. Some parents refused to take their children to a psychologist, while others stated that the children themselves were unwilling to do so. The reasons for this are, of course, well understood.

In general terms, the following table can be presented about the attitude of parents to children in the process of socialization.

TABLE 1. Ratio of responses in problem and healthy families.

Generalized answers	
Indicators for a healthy family	Indicators for a troubled family
I consider it my duty to know what my child thinks.	I always understand my child.
I respect my child.	I feel sympathy for the child.
Good parents try to keep their child away from life's difficulties.	It is necessary to raise a child in a strict regime so that he becomes a good person.
I always try to help my child.	I get involved in everything my child does.
I really like it when my child's friends come to our house.	I spend all my free time with my child with pleasure.
I happily spend all my free time with my child.	As I see my child growing up and getting older, I often
I wish my child to achieve everything that I could not achieve in life.	Parents should not demand that the child adapt to them, they themselves should adapt to him.
Parents should not demand that the child adapt to them, they themselves should adapt to him.	I try to fulfill all my child's requests.
I try to fulfill all my child's requests.	When making decisions in the family, the child's opinion should also be taken into account.
I am very interested in my child's life.	I am very interested in my child's life.
During a conflict with a child, I can often admit that the child is right in his own way.	I always take the child's opinion into account.
I maintain friendly relations with my child.	I maintain friendly relations with my child.
The most important thing is that the child has a calm and carefree childhood.	I always take the child's opinion into account.
I understand my child's sorrows	I foster friendships with my child.
I like my child just the way he is.	Raising a child is completely nerve-racking.
I take great care of my child's health.	I share my child's interests.
I am proud of my child	I am proud of my child.

As can be seen from the table, these relationships are influenced by many factors of the social environment and the personality of the parents themselves.

Thus, the number of psychologists and social educators working in rural regions is significantly lower than in the city of Baku, and the general population lacks substantial information on this issue. Therefore, it is imperative to raise public awareness. Children may also be referred to school psychologists. However, we cannot assess the effectiveness of school psychologists who employ only a single method, similar to the approach of others in comparable positions.

Overall, an analysis of the primary directions of psychosocial work with children and adolescents from problematic families, as well as their socialization processes, reveals that specialists are familiar with correctional and psychotherapeutic methods for working with children and adolescents. However, they face specific difficulties in applying these methods. The primary reason for this challenge is the deterioration of the broader social environment. Parents, class teachers, school psychologists, and field doctors must engage in comprehensive work in this domain, structuring their efforts based on specialized projects and programs.

In examining the characteristics of psychosocial assistance provided to children by parents and specialists within the framework of social adaptation, and considering various aspects of psy-

chological behavior correction, it became evident that the current level of intervention aimed at identifying and addressing psychological issues in children and adolescents is insufficient, particularly when taking into account the documented psychological deviations in their behavior. Surveys of parents, school psychologists, and directors of psychological centers revealed that the level of training of psychologists and social educators for conducting psychological rehabilitation of children and adolescents is inadequate. Furthermore, the practical implementation of their knowledge is constrained by several social factors, including the insufficient pedagogical and psychological preparation of parents, the limited involvement of children from disadvantaged families in the work of school psychologists and class teachers. An analysis of both domestic and international literature and practical experience indicates that a comprehensive, integrated approach is necessary to effectively address the needs of pedagogically weak families and children with psychosomatic issues.

In recent years, many parents have developed the misguided belief that by satisfying all their child's financial desires and dreams, they are fulfilling their responsibilities in caring for and educating them. This belief is fundamentally flawed. For children to mature into responsible citizens of society and the state, it is crucial that parents guide them with a sense of duty and responsibility. Consequently, parents must prioritize their children's needs over their own and take all possible measures to ensure their children's future is healthy and secure.

The responsibility of raising children should not rest solely with parents but must also involve educators. Once children enter school, teachers must play an active role in guiding them and doing everything possible to shield them from harmful behaviors. If children become indifferent to their education and absenteeism increases, it is the teachers' responsibility to inform the parents. I concluded that the teachers justified their actions and those of the parents, and even found their indifferent attitude somewhat tolerable. This represents a major issue. Many children in foreign countries seek freedom and resist their family's authority, creating a foundation for numerous social problems. It is no coincidence that children are most affected by this issue. Their premature desire for freedom facilitates the rapid infiltration of such disruptions into the family structure.

At the age of 7-8, a specialized method is used to assess children's relationships with family members. A situation is created that mimics family scenarios, where roles are portrayed by animal offspring. The child, upon observing these images, explains and evaluates the protagonist's relationship with their parents, siblings, and others. The child's narrative reflects their actual emotional responses, revealing their desires and fears.

Children's attitudes toward their families can also be assessed through their drawings. Negative emotions are reflected when children omit or place family members at the edges of their drawings, or separate them from the rest of the family with objects. When they draw without emotional engagement, it indicates a detachment. Children are generally enthusiastic about drawing, viewing it as a form of play.

To study the influence of family dynamics on the development of a child's personality, techniques such as completing unfinished sentences, sociometric analysis, and children's narratives can be employed. These methods provide insight into how mutually interested the child and their parents are in each other's lives.

What personal expectations does the child hold during their interactions? These expectations are shaped by emotional connections with the parents. When a child experiences emotional “distress,” they tend to withdraw, becoming introverted and obstinate. Pessimistic or optimistic moods arise primarily from the nature of these interactions.

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